

MODELLING OF THE PUSHING INSTALLATION OF OPTICAL FIBER CABLE IN URBAN AREA

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SUMMARY : The spreading of whole optical access networks for the customers (FTTH , FTTB,...) connecting necessitates to master some mechanical parameters like optical fiber cable structure. The studied cable presents a multilayer cylindrical structure. The analytical constitutive equations have been obtained with homogenization techniques on multilayer cylindrical beam. A Timoshenko's approach is used without transverse shear correction. Some mechanical tests have been performed such as simple tensile tests , bending coupled with tension test and buckling tests. The cable buckling behavior is the first global approach studied in this paper. The buckling test results are provided by a bench test for pushing installation fully manufactured by the CNET. A modelling with finite elements using explicit method of ABAQUS software simulate the cable installation by pushing process. The stiffness matrix terms are validated by those experimental tests. The experimental buckling results are close to theoretical buckling results and 2-D numerical results.

KEYWORDS : linear elasticity, isotropic transverse beam, oriented composite layer, cable installation, pipe buckling, cable pushing bench test, finite element modelling.

INTRODUCTION

The fiber optical expansion is more and more important in access networks. The development of new cable structures must integrate the cable installation process constraints. In the urban area, the choice between a pulling and a pushing installation or a mixture of both depends on the length to install, the course dependent constraints, the nature of the ducts and the optical fiber cable mechanical characteristics. The pushing technique consists in applying a pushing effort on cable at the beginning of the duct. The optical cable flexional mode is the major mode occurring in this process. Our study is about the cable mechanical characteristics identification and its pushing installation process.

The studied optical fiber cable is considered like a composite material by its multilayer cylindrical structure and by its different components like hdPE, PCV, kelvar, glass-resin. The hdPE and PCV layers are transversely isotropic and the kevlar layer is anisotropic due to its helical twisted yarns (Fig. 1). The analytical constitutive equations are given for a multilayer cylindrical beam. The Hashin's model [1] is used to calculate the equivalent elastic constants

of kevlar and glass-resin layers. After writing the local behavior law for each layer in consecutive three-dimensional basis and reducing it in one dimension, the generalised behavior law is established with the help of integration techniques. The obtained stiffness matrix terms are compared with the stiffness moduli provided by tensile tests, bending and buckling tests.

A cable installation bench test is manufactured to understand the cable global behavior and to predict the cable buckling. The cable is introduced under a compressive axial load, inside translucent ducts. The buckling theories of pipes installed for the petrol drilling permit us to analyse the phenomena observed during the cable pushing process. The cable helix pitches in the helical configuration and the axial loads at the end-up of the duct are studied. Then a finite element modelling of cable pushing process is compared to the experimental data.

STRUCTURE CABLE STUDY

Homogenization techniques

The multilayer cable is supposed transversely isotropic in the axial direction. The local behavior law (Eqn 1) under transversely isotropic assumptions is expressed in the principal fiber direction (L,T,R) of each layer [2]. The Fig. 2 represents the three different basis (L,T,R), (X,R,θ),(X,Y,Z) used to express the constitutive equations. We have stress-strain relations in the (L,T,R) coordinate system :

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \left. \begin{array}{l}
 \sigma_{LL} \\
 \sigma_{TT} \\
 \sigma_{RR} \\
 \sigma_{TR} \\
 \sigma_{LR} \\
 \sigma_{LT}
 \end{array} \right\} = \begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \psi E_L & 2\nu_{LT}K_T & 2\nu_{LT}K_T & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\
 2\nu_{LT}K_T & K_T + G_{TT} & K_T - G_{TT} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\
 2\nu_{LT}K_T & K_T - G_{TT} & K_T + G_{TT} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{TT} & 0 & 0 & \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{LT} & 0 & \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{LT}
 \end{array} \left. \begin{array}{l}
 \epsilon_{LL} \\
 \epsilon_{TT} \\
 \epsilon_{RR} \\
 \epsilon_{TR} \\
 \epsilon_{LR} \\
 \epsilon_{LT}
 \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)
 \end{array}$$

Fig.1 : Multilayer cable.

Fig. 2 : The three coordinate systems used.

This law is written in a common reference to the layers set, the local cylindrical (X,R,θ) coordinate system . The C16, C26, C36 et C45 coupling terms appear in the stiffness matrix (Eqn 2). The Cij terms depend on the cosines direction (cos α, sin α) from the first coordinate transformation and the five independent elastic constants E_L, E_T, G_{LT}, G_{TT}, ν_{LT}, K_T of each homogenised layer. The twist angle of the kevlar yarn is α . We notice that the C16, C26, C36

et C45 coupling terms are null for the PCV, hdPE transversely isotropic layers and the glass-resin layer because there is no twist angle for those layers.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{XX} \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta} \\ \sigma_{RR} \\ \sigma_{\theta R} \\ \sigma_{RX} \\ \sigma_{X\theta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C11 & C12 & C13 & 0 & 0 & C16 \\ C12 & C22 & C23 & 0 & 0 & C26 \\ C13 & C23 & C33 & 0 & 0 & C36 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C44 & C45 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C45 & C55 & 0 \\ C16 & C26 & C36 & 0 & 0 & C66 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{XX} \\ \epsilon_{\theta\theta} \\ \epsilon_{RR} \\ \epsilon_{\theta R} \\ \epsilon_{RX} \\ \epsilon_{X\theta} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C11 &= C \psi E_L + K_T(4S^2C^2v_{LT} + S^4) + S^4G_{TT} + 4C^2S^2G_{LT} \\ C12 &= S^2C^2\psi E_L + K_T(2v_{LT}(S^4 + C^4) + C^2S^2) + C^2S^2G_{TT} - 4C^2S^2G_{LT} \\ C13 &= (2C^2v_{LT} + S^2)K_T - S^2G_{TT} \\ C22 &= S^4\psi E_L + K_T(C^4 + 4C^2S^2v_{LT}) + C^4G_{TT} + 4S^2C^2G_{LT} \\ C23 &= K_T(C^2 + 2S^2v_{LT}) - C^2G_{TT} \\ C33 &= K_T + G_{TT} \\ C44 &= C^2G_{TT} + S^2G_{LT} \\ C45 &= -(G_{TT} - G_{LT})SC \\ C55 &= S^2G_{TT} + C^2G_{LT} \\ C66 &= S^2C^2\psi E_L + K_T(-4v_{LT}(S^2 + C^2) + C^2S^2) + C^2S^2G_{TT} + (C^2 - S^2)G_{LT} \\ C16 &= (C^3S \psi E_L - K_T(2v_{LT}(C^3S - CS^3) - CS^3) - S^3C G_{TT} - 2C S (C^2 - S^2)G_{LT}) \\ C26 &= (C S^3\psi E_L - K_T(2v_{LT}(C S^3 - C^3S) - CS^3) - S C^3G_{TT} + 2C S (C^2 - S^2)G_{LT}) \\ C36 &= -C S (K_T(1 - 2v_{LT}) - G_{TT}) \end{aligned}$$

with $C = \cos\alpha; S = \sin\alpha$

The beam theory with Timoshenko’s hypothesis including transverse shear is applied. The consequence on the constitutive equations is the neglecting of the following stresses components, $\sigma_{RR}, \sigma_{\theta\theta}, \sigma_{R\theta}$ in comparison with the other stresses components. The reduced local constitutive equations (Eqn 3) in the (X,R, θ) coordinate system are obtained with the \bar{C}_{ij} terms depending linearly on the preceding Cij terms.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{XX} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \sigma_{RX} \\ \sigma_{X\theta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C11 & C12 & C13 & 0 & 0 & C16 \\ C12 & C22 & C23 & 0 & 0 & C26 \\ C13 & C23 & C33 & 0 & 0 & C36 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C44 & C45 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C45 & C55 & 0 \\ C16 & C26 & C36 & 0 & 0 & C66 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{XX} \\ \epsilon_{\theta\theta} \\ \epsilon_{RR} \\ \epsilon_{\theta R} \\ \epsilon_{RX} \\ \epsilon_{X\theta} \end{pmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{XX} \\ \sigma_{X\theta} \\ \sigma_{RX} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{C}16 & \bar{C}16 & 0 \\ \bar{C}16 & \bar{C}16 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{C}16 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{XX} \\ \epsilon_{X\theta} \\ \epsilon_{RX} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The Eqn 3 are now expressed in the Cartesian (X, Y, Z) coordinate system. The new reduced local stiffness matrix is a function of the cosines direction ($\cos\theta, \sin\theta$) from the second coordinate transformation. The stress-strain relations in the Cartesian (X, Y, Z) coordinate system are defined by the Eqn 4:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{XX} \\ \sigma_{XY} \\ \sigma_{XZ} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \overline{cC11} & \overline{sC16} & -\overline{cC16} \\ \overline{sC16} & c^2\overline{C55} + s^2\overline{C66} & c\overline{s(-C66 + C55)} \\ -\overline{cC16} & c\overline{s(-C66 + C55)} & s^2\overline{C55} + c^2\overline{C66} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{XX} \\ \varepsilon_{XY} \\ \varepsilon_{XZ} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad \begin{matrix} c = \cos\theta \\ s = \sin\theta \end{matrix} \quad (4)$$

The generalised efforts components (N,Ty,Tz) and generalised moments components (Mx,My,Mz) are obtained by the integration of the Eqn 4 in the circular cross section. We have the global reduced behavior law expressed by the relation (5). The \overline{Ckl} terms of the stiffness matrix is the summation of the $(R_k^x - R_{k-1}^x)$ thickness and \overline{Cij} terms multiplication of each layer denoted by k. One can notice that the transverse shear correction obtained by the Hellinger-Reissner's functional mixed approach is not presented here. The matrix diagonal terms of the Eqn 5 are used to be compared to the experimental and numerical results.

$$\begin{pmatrix} N \\ Ty \\ Tz \\ Mx \\ My \\ Mz \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \overline{C11}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C14}' & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \overline{C22}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C25}' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \overline{C22}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C36}' \\ \overline{C14}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C44}' & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \overline{C25}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C55}' & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \overline{C36}' & 0 & 0 & \overline{C55}' \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_X^0 \\ 2\varepsilon_{XY}^0 \\ 2\varepsilon_{XZ}^0 \\ \chi_X \\ \chi_Y \\ \chi_Z \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{C11}' = \sum_k \overline{C11}^k p (R_k^2 - R_{k-1}^2)$$

$$\overline{C22}' = \sum_k (\overline{C66}^k + \overline{C55}^k) p (R_k^2 - R_{k-1}^2) / 2$$

$$\overline{C44}' = \sum_k (\overline{C66}^k + \overline{C55}^k) p (R_k^4 - R_{k-1}^4) / 4$$

$$\overline{C55}' = \sum_k \overline{C11}^k p (R_k^4 - R_{k-1}^4) / 4$$

$$\overline{C14}' = \sum_k \overline{C16}^k 2p (R_k^3 - R_{k-1}^3) / 3$$

$$\overline{C25}' = \sum_k \overline{C16}^k (-p) (R_k^3 - R_{k-1}^3) / 3$$

$$\overline{C36}' = \sum_k \overline{C16}^k p (R_k^3 - R_{k-1}^3) / 3$$

Global stiffness matrix validation

During the cable installation in the urban area, the stiffness moduli of traction $\overline{C11}'$, bending $\overline{C55}'$ and twist $\overline{C44}'$ are mainly involved. The validation of these terms in the global stiffness matrix (Eqn 5) is made in comparison with the same moduli obtained by numerical simulations, characterisation tests. At another level, those terms are also compared to the

results of another behavior law with orthotropic components [3]. These different comparisons are described below :

- Simple tests such as tensile test, bending tests and twist tests on a multilayer cylinder are modelled using finite element ABAQUS software. Several numerical cases are studied to validate the global stiffness matrix (Table 1). The case 1 is about a cylinder constituted by several isotropic layers. The case 2 concerns the simulation of a cylinder composed by isotropic and anisotropic layers without twist angle.
- The analytical comparison with [3] is about a configuration with a oriented kevlar yarn. The case 3 and the case 4 concern a cylinder with isotropic and anisotropic layers with respectively a kevlar yarn twist angle of 4° and 45°.
- The characterisation tests are made with optical fiber cable in which the kevlar yarn twist angle is 4°. The tensile test is realised with a length of 50 meters according to France Telecom standards. The bending test coupled with tensile effort realised at the ENSAM's Structure Laboratory necessitates a special devices setting (Fig. 3).

The Table 1 summarizes the stiffness moduli comparisons. Error percentages on the rigidity moduli are provided by the different configurations cited above and the values obtained by the global stiffness matrix (Eqn 5). For the case 3, the analytical values are $\overline{C_{11}} = 0.095 \text{ N.m}^2$, $\overline{C_{44}} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ N.m}^4$, $\overline{C_{55}} = 1.9 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ N.m}^4$. Errors are inferior than 5 % excepted to the modulus $\overline{C_{44}}$ of case 4. One can conclude that with any geometrical and mechanical characteristics of each cable layer the diagonal terms of the global stiffness matrix can be calculated and used to simulate numerically the pushing installation process.

Table 1 : Error percentage of stiffness moduli.

Error in %		<u>case 1 :</u> multilayer with isotropic materials	<u>case 2 :</u> multilayer without twist angle	<u>case 3 :</u> multilayer with kevlar layer at $\alpha=4^\circ$	<u>case 4 :</u> multilayer with kevlar layer at $\alpha=45^\circ$
global matrix compared to	$\overline{C_{kl}}$				
Numerical Simulations (ABAQUS)	$\overline{C_{11}}$	0,03	0,01	-	-
	$\overline{C_{44}}$	0,03	0,05	-	-
	$\overline{C_{55}}$	-1,71	0,02	-	-
Analytical Behavior from [3]	$\overline{C_{11}}$	-	-	0,5	-5,9
	$\overline{C_{44}}$	-	-	1,8	17,5
	$\overline{C_{55}}$	-	-	0,5	-5,9
Tensile Test	$\overline{C_{11}}$	-	-	-4,4	-
Bending Test	$\overline{C_{55}}$	-	-	-6,7	-

CABLE BUCKLING IN DUCT

Cable pushing bench test

A full-size bench test is realised at the C.N.E.T.'s facilities to understand the cable global behavior and to provide data to validate the pushing numerical simulations. It is composed by

a pusher engine, a motorised reel, translucent ducts and a computer (Fig. 4). Two effort sensors installed on either side of the pusher engine give the pushing effort F_{push} , a counting wheel provides the introduced length, a third sensor placed at the up-end of the duct informs us on the stop effort, F_{stop} . This stop points out the up-end of the course. All data are recorded on the computer which pilots the test.

Fig. 3 : The bending test.

Fig. 4 : The pushing bench test.

The studied multilayer fiber optic cable is pushed on a length of 45 meters. During the pushing test, one can observe that first the cable keeps its pre-stressed configuration and lies inside the duct. Then lateral displacements in sinusoidal shape appear under a higher compressive load F_{push} . If the compressive axial load F_{push} gets more and more important, the cable buckles into a new helical shape. The Fig. 5 shows the buckled cable in a horizontal translucent PCV duct at the end of the test. The more the cable undulations increase, the more the contact force increases. The created frictional force provoked by this contact force also prevents the cable introduction. It's interesting to know how to predict this helical configuration. This study of the cable buckling is about the axial load influency on the helix pitch and the axial load distribution along the duct.

Fig. 5 : A buckled cable in a translucent PCV duct.

Theoretical study

Two formula express the compressive axial force F_{push} as a function of the cable helix pitch P and its bending stiffness modulus EI . [4] discussed about their meaning. They differ by a factor of two .

$$F_{push} = 8\pi^2 * \frac{(EI)}{P^2} \Leftrightarrow \frac{P}{2} = \sqrt{2} \pi \sqrt{\frac{EI}{F_{push}}} \quad (6)$$

$$F_{push} = 4\pi^2 * \frac{(EI)}{P^2} \Leftrightarrow \frac{P}{2} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{EI}{F_{push}}} \quad (7)$$

According to [5], when the compressive axial load F_{push} reaches a limiting value F_{cr} , the cable buckles into a sinusoidal shape. This first buckling load F_{cr} is given in the Eqn 8. If the axial load is greater than the critical load, the helical shape will be developed in a helix around the duct wall. The helical buckling load expression (Eqn 9) for a long cable in horizontal duct is a function of the cable bending modulus EI , the weight w and the clearance radius r in the duct.

$$F_{cr} = 2 \sqrt{\frac{EI w}{r}} \quad (8)$$

$$F_{hel} = 2 \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{EI w}{r}} \quad (9)$$

The following differential equation for the axial load of a helically buckled weighty cable in a inclined duct is given in [4] and expresses in the Eqn 10 :

$$\frac{dF}{dX} = \mu (w \sin \beta + w_n) - w \cos \beta \quad \text{where } w_n = \frac{r F_{push}^2}{4 EI} \quad (10)$$

which is a function of the weight w , the friction coefficient μ , the contact force w_n , the incline angle β and the helical length X measured from down-up. The axial load F distribution for helically buckled cable in a horizontal duct under is written in the Eqn 11 :

$$F(X) = \sqrt{\frac{4 EI w}{r}} \tan \left(\mu X \sqrt{\frac{r w}{4 EI}} + \arctan \left(F_{push} \sqrt{\frac{r}{4 EI w}} \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

Experimental helical configuration study

A cable is pushed in a duct of 45 meters. When the test is finished, the helix pitches are collected. The cable helix pitches vary along the translucent duct. The Fig. 6 shows us several sets of helix pitches with the same value. There are 83 half periods. The graph can be divided by two parts or maybe more : the (1-39) set collection corresponds to a half helix pitch average of 36 cm, and the (40-83) set collection corresponds to a half helix pitch average of 68 cm. The whole half helix pitches average is about 53 cm. One can notice that the compressive axial load influences more the cable buckling on the down-up of the duct.

Fig. 6 : The cable periods collection in a duct of 45 meters.

It is interesting to extract the helix pitch P from the Eqns 6 and 7, and to compare it to the P experimental values. It is also an original way to validate the bending stiffness modulus from the Eqn 5.

Compressive axial load evolution

The Fig. 7 shows us the efforts F_{push} and F_{stop} recordings during the test on 45 meters. This figure can be divided into three parts from the viewpoint of the F_{push} increasing. In the part A, as the up-end cable extremity is free, the stop force F_{stop} remains stationary, also the compressive axial load F_{push} does. In the part B, the cable reaches the stop. It's why the F_{stop} increases and remains stationary to 10 daN. The F_{push} increases equally until the maximum cable length introduced in the duct is reached. There is a sharp peak at 140 daN which delimits the part C. In this last part, the down-up cable extremity folds inside the duct under the excessive axial load. The F_{push} decreasing corresponds to a new introduction of the folded cable. At the down-up of the duct, the cable forms a buckle in 8 shape. The pushing force limit is overflow. The cable is damaged after this test. Normally, we have to stop the cable introduction before reaching the helix configuration to conserve the cable optical functions.

We substitute these recorded F_{push} data into Eqns 6 and 7 and obtain the curves $P/2(6)$ and $P/2(7)$ (Fig.7). These former inform us on the values before and after the cable reaches the stop at 44,8 meters. The helix pitch is inversely proportional to the compressive axial load. The smaller the axial load F_{push} is, the higher the helix pitch P is as the curves $P/2(6)$ and $P/2(7)$ show us.

Fig. 7 : Efforts F_{push} and F_{stop} recordings and $P/2$ deduced from Eqns 6 and 7.

According to Eqn 9, the helical buckling configuration appears for a F_{push} minimum value of 25 daN :

$$F_{hel} = 2 \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\frac{EI w}{r}} \cong 25 \text{ daN}$$

We can compare the $P/2$ values in the Figs. 6 and 7. We study the helix pitches when the cable starts buckling and when the test is stopped :

- The experimental $P/2$ values observed at the end-up of the duct are in relation with the beginning of the cable buckling (i.e. when the axial load F_{push} reaches the buckling load, F_{hel}). For a buckling load value of 25 daN, the half helix pitches corresponding values are about 50 cm and 80 cm respectively for the $P/2(7)$ and $P/2(6)$ curves (Fig. 7). The experimental $P/2$ average is about 68 cm and is framed by the preceding values.
- The experimental $P/2$ values at the down-up of the duct correspond to the final helical configuration. For a F_{push} value of 80 daN, the half helix pitches corresponding values are about 35 cm and 50 cm respectively for $P/2(7)$ and $P/2(6)$ curves. The experimental $P/2$ average is about 36 cm and is equally coherent with the theoretical values.

End-up axial load calculation

For a configuration of the bench test described below, we calculate the axial load distribution at the $X=45$ m from the Eqn 11. The cable/duct friction coefficient is 0.2. The effective weight is 0.12 kg/m. The cable Young modulus is $8 \cdot 10^9$ N/m². The clearance radius is 0.038 m. We find a F_{push} equal to 50 daN for a load $F(X)$ given to 10 daN. According to the part B of the Fig. 7, the F_{push} value is coherent. The stationary stage of the end-up load F_{stop} at 10 daN begins at a F_{push} value of 40 daN.

Numerical simulations

A 2-D finite element modelling is used to simulate the cable pushing in a duct. Beam finite elements with two nodes at 3 degrees of freedom a node, using the Timoshenko's approach simulate the cable. Rigid elements simulate the duct. The simulation size is 12671 degrees of freedom. The explicit version on the ABAQUS software allows us to treat this non linear contact problem. The results of a cable pushing on a 5 meters long duct are compared to the numerical results for three duct diameters : 0.025 m, 0.040 m, 0.060 m (Fig. 8). The Table 2 represents the up-end force F_{stop} and the sinus and helix pitches comparisons. The numerical results are coherent for the pitch. But further they will have to be more improved as compared to the experimental compressive stop load.

Table 2 : Experimental and numerical comparisons on a 5meters duct.

Duct diameter m	Numerical results		Experimental results	
	F_{stop} N	sinus pitch m	F_{stop} N	helix pitch m
0.025	1015	0,50	670	0,57
0.040	646	0,72	450	0,73
0.060	357	0,85	210	0,89

Fig 8 : Sinusoidal buckling configuration with 2D numerical simulation.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The analytical global stiffness matrix established for an oriented multilayer cylinder corresponds to the characteristic mechanics of the studied optical fiber cable. This stiffness matrix can be used for any isotropic transverse oriented multilayer cylinder. These calculated stiffness moduli are injected in the pushing numerical modelling.

2. The pushing experimental study permits us to understand the cable global behavior. The buckling theoretical relations applied to the pipes for petrol drilling afford us to understand the different configurations of cable buckling.
3. The 2-D finite element modelling of the cable pushing process is relatively close to the experimental values. Further this modelling will have to be more improved. A length representative of urban area configuration will be studied. The 3-D numerical approach using beam elements at 9 degrees of freedom a node for the cable and pipe elements for the duct will be studied. The numerical simulation will be a reliable tool to simulate the cable installation by pushing. This tool could be used to anticipate the conception of a new cable structure.

NOTATIONS

σ_{IJ} : stress component, G_{TT} : Coulomb's transverse modulus, ν_{LT} : Poisson's coefficient, ϵ_{IJ} : strain component, N : axial force, M_i : moment in the direction i , α : twist angle, F_{push} : compressive axial load, w : cable weight per unit length, μ : cable/duct friction coefficient, $E I$: cable bending modulus, F_{hel} : helical buckling load, X : helically bucked length of a duct measured from down-up, $1 \text{ cm} = 0.01 \text{ m}$.	K_T : lateral shrinking modulus, G_{LT} : Coulomb's axial modulus, E_L : axial stiffness modulus, C_{ij} : stiffness matrix component, T_i : transverse force in direction i , k : cylinder layer index, θ : transformation angle, F_{stop} : axial effort in the up-end of the duct, P : helix pitch, r : clearance radius between cable and duct, F_{cr} : sinusoidal buckling load, $F(X)$: up-end axial load at the distance X , w_n : contact force resulting from helical buckling of weightless cable, $1 \text{ daN} = 10 \text{ N}$.
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